

ROLE OF EDUCATION IN THE PROTECTION OF WOMEN'S SAFETY AND DIGNITY

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MUSIC THERAPY AS A TOOL TO CONTROL CARDIOVASCULAR AND NEUROENDOCRINE DISORDERS IN HOUSEHOLD WOMEN.

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ABSTRACT

It is a well-known fact that after a time period household women feel isolation and aloneness, especially innuclear family may be due to many reason such as children become adult, husband busy in job, routine life style etc. As a result of this they will face various cardiovascular (CVD) and neuroendocrine (NED) disorders such anxiety, hypertension, asphyxia, irregular Menstrual cycle, unusual B.P., Headache, insomnia etc. To overcome them they will start using various type of medicine as prescribed by their physician. There is no debut that medicine have the ability to cure them, but on the other side it is a well establish fact that each medicine have some short of side effects on their body and sometime side effects are converting in to serious problems leading upto death. Peoples are using Music therapy since time immemorial. According to Hindu mythology, music originated with the first sound ever to be heard in the universe, the Naadbrahma, or Om. Samveda is full of music and its use. In 400B.C. Hippocrates, known as the father of Medicine, played music to soothe his patients. Aristotle described music as a force that purified emotions. Research on the effects of music therapy in healthcare hasbeen grown rapidly during the past 20 years and has included a variety of outcome measures in a wide range of specialty areas including medical care, geriatric care, and rehabilitation. Music therapy is incorporated in a number of medicines. Some of these include pregnancy, oncology, CVD, pain management, physical rehabilita-tion and paediatrics. Music therapy has been shown to influence the immune system, BP, Heart and respiratory rates and pain perception. I observed that the specific pleasant sounds in form of music affect the physiology of female rat and women by altering the levels of biochemical, hormonal and haematological parameters such as serum total cholesterol, triglycerides, VLDL and LDL, HDL, adrenalin, endorphin, estragon, gonadotropins and progesterone which control CVD and NED in household women. Findings gain support from the work if Fukul and Toyoshima (2008) who observed that music influence and affect the cranial nerves in humans from foetus to adult and facilitates the neurogenesis and repair of cerebral nerves by adjusting the secretion of steroid hormones, ultimately leading to cerebral plasticity. Music affects levels of such steroids as cortisol, testosterone and estro-gen, and we believe that music also affects the receptor genes related to these substances, and related proteins.

INTRODUCTION

Today we are living in sea of various type of chemicals which responsible for creating various types of serious diseases or disorder, to cure them we are again using chemicals in form of drugs. There is no debut that drugs have the ability to cure disease and disorders but on the other side it is also a well-established fact that each drug has some short of side effects and sometime side effects are converted in to serious problems. It is an established fact that brain is controlling entire metabolism, gene activation, biochemistry, haematology, physi-ology etc. of the body through different mechanisms and if any mechanism disturbed by any agents it reflects in form of disease or disorder. So anything which is capable to influence the brain also influences the entire metabolism and physiology of body. No debut this can be done by sound vibrations in form of music. The Pleasant sounds can be defined as combination of both natural sounds, cultural and historic sounds. Because the acous-tical environment is made up of many sounds the wellbeing of acoustical environment depends on interactions between the amplitudes and frequencies of all the sounds. Acoustical environment, as a stimulus has different properties on livings specially humans. Music induces mood change in either a depressive or a vigour direction.

No one can deny the fact that we feel cool and calm when a bird sang or a mammal or amphibian vocalized or air blows in a forest. We observed that the natural sounds have their impact on the physiology of living by altering the levels of biochemical and haematological parameters.

Music is a new field in therapeutic use. Music therapy is incorporated in a number of medicines. Some of these include pregnancy, oncology, CVD, pain management, physical rehabilitation and paediatrics. Music therapy has been shown to influence the immune system, BP, Heart and respiratory rates and pain perception.

Music therapy is also increasingly used in end-of-life care, with a growing number of music therapists being employed in hospices and hospital-based palliative care programs each year (Hilliard 2005). Data from a survey study of 300 randomly selected hospices in the U.S. indicated that the most popular forms of complementary therapies were massage therapy and music therapy (Demmer 2004). This is also true for use of complementary therapies in Canadian hospices, according to a recently completed survey (Oneschuk 2007). Music therapists in end-of-life care work with a broad range of populations with many types of illnesses including cancer (Hanser 2005; Hilliard 2003; Magill 2001), HIV/AIDS (Lee 1996; Neugebauer 1999), congestive heart failure (Dileo 2005c), dementia (Patrick 2005) and neurodegenerative disorders (Magee 2004; Scheiby 2005). The primary aim of music therapy in this context is to improve a person's quality of life by helping relieve symptoms, addressing psychological needs, offering support and comfort, facilitating communication, and meeting spiritual needs. In addition, music therapists assist family and caregivers with coping, communication, and grief/bereavement (Dileo 2005b).

I have also completed a project to analyse the impact of music therapy on albino rats and humans and I observed that the specific pleasant sounds in form of music affect the physiology of rat and human by altering the levels of biochemical and haematological parameters such as significant decrease in serum total cholesterol, non-significant decrease in triglycerides, non-significant decrease in VLDL and LDL, significant increase in HDL in most

Background-

- Peoples are using Music therapy since time immemorial. According to Hindu mythology, music originated with the first sound ever to be heard in the universe, the Naadbrahma, or Om. Samveda is full of music and its use.
- Graet Tansen use the music for beneficial purpose.
- Early Egyptian and Greeks used music to heal specific ailments, and Apollo was the God of music & medicine.
- In 400B.C. Hippocrates, known as the father of Medicine, played music to soothe his patients. Aristotle described music as a force that purified emotions.
- MT is evident in Biblical scriptures and historical writings of ancient civilizations such as Egypt, China, Greece and Rome.
- Harp music has been prescribed instead of tranquilizers and painkillers for cancer patients at the University of Massachusetts Medical Centre.
- Vincent & Thompson (1928)² use radio, gramophone music to control B.P.
- In a 1995 study it was found that surgeons, who listened to the music of their choice while performing operations, were found to have lower BP and slower heart rate and could perform mental tasks more quickly and accurately.
- A professor of music and psychiatry Dr. Paul Robertson of Kingston University, Ontario, Canada, shares studied that show that patient who are exposed to 15 minutes of soothing music require only half the recom-

mended dose of sedatives and anaesthetic drugs for painful operations.

- In 1998, NAMT (1950) joined forces with another music therapy organization to become as the American Music Therapy Association (AMTA).
- In this line Indian Association of Music Therapy (IAMT) was established in 2010

Research on the effects of music and music therapy in healthcare has grown rapidly during the past 20 years and has included a variety of outcome measures in a wide range of specialty areas including medical care, geriatric care, and rehabilitation. It is important, however, to make a clear distinction between music interventions administered by medical or healthcare professionals (music medicine) and those implemented by trained music therapists (music therapy). A substantive set of data indicates that music therapy interventions are more effective than music medicine interventions for improving physiological as well as psychological outcomes in medical patients. This difference might be attributed to the fact that music therapists individualize their interventions to meet patients' specific needs, more actively engage the patients in the music making, make use of the therapeutic relationship established with the patient to meet clinical goals and employ a systematic therapeutic process that includes assessment, treatment, and evaluation. As defined by Dileo 1999, interventions are categorized as 'music medicine' when passive listening to pre-recorded music is offered by medical personnel. In contrast, music therapy requires the implementation of a music intervention by a trained music therapist, the presence of a therapeutic process, and the use of personally tailored music experiences.

Observations -

Research outcome explain the use of music therapy in NED in household women-Anxiety, Schizophrenic, Treatment of drug abuse, Multiple sclerosis, Psychological rehabilitation, Alzheimer Disease, Dementia, Autism, Epilepsy, Conversation skills apply to music, Non verbal vocalizations, Early word combinations

Research outcome explain the use of Music Therapy in CVD and other disorders in household women-To Control B.P., Heart Rate, respiratory rate, anxiety & pain in coronary angiography, Mean arterial pressure, asphyxia, Cancer therapy, Pain Care Management, Dose of anesthesia ? and Electromyography (EMG) shows muscle by relaxation

Material Methods-

Selection of Music (Test compound)

Music is selected on the basis of their property. Three sets of pre-recorded Indian classical (Specific Indian ragas) and natural environmental sound are selected on the basis of trial and error methods. They are given to the experimental animals for a period of 90 days. The results were analyzed and after that the similar sound treatment are given to volunteers for a period of 90 days. The biochemical analysis of blood samples are carried at 30 days, 60 days and 90 days interval. The blood samples of volunteers are collected by a physician hire for the purpose, whereas the blood of albino rats was taken in lab from treated and control groups.

Sound of specific Indian ragas and Recording of natural habitat are given at 55-65 db (controlled by sound meter) to albino rat for two hours (9-10 AM and 3-4 PM) daily by speakers attached to the wall of their cage for 30, 60, 90 days through, whereas human volunteers are allowed to listen to specific sounds through headphones at their home (for the same time period as to rats) after training them in workshops organized in dept' on Sundays and holidays.

Control groups of both rats and humans are also assigned to listening to taped "white noise" ("White noise" or "synthetic silence" is an attempt to block out environmental noise. In this case it was a pre-nature sounds such as sea sounds, which themselves were rhythmic) through headphones, or to a control group.

Selection of Individuals-

Albino Rats: For the experimentation individuals selected randomly irrespective of sex. Five healthy adult albino rats (68 weeks of age, with average body weight of 150200 g) were selected randomly for test and control studies their blood was collected after 30, 60 and 90 days for the present investigation. Each rat was assigned a number for convenience prior to experimentation.

Volunteers-The Volunteers were selected through a wide publicity (News paper, SMS, TV Programmes) from Agra, Noida, Delhi, Ghaziabad, Gurgaon region. They are provided to fill a questionnaire. On the basis of a questionnaire they are provide a recorded CD of selected songs and sounds.

Collection of Blood Samples-The blood from rats collected in the early morning hours (7-8 AM) in lab on the scheduled date. The blood samples were obtained with the help of 2.0 ml disposable syringe from the tail albino rats, whereas the blood samples of human were collected by a physician hired for the purpose. The various biochemical parameters of rats were analyzed with the help of a standard kit methods in dept lab, while human blood test are conducted in authorize labs of a respective city.

What is Sound ?

- Noise, which is often referred to as unwanted sound, is typically, characterized by the intensity frequency, periodicity (continuous or intermittent) and duration of sound. Unwanted sound to some may be considered wanted sound by others, as in the case of loud music (Talbot, 1995).
- Sound Pollution, which is often referred to as greater than normal frequency.
- Music Therapy, which is often referred to Rhythmic desired sound of specific frequency and pressure of choice at specific type & time.

Relation between music therapy and science (Bio-musicology)-

- As per Scientific theories-All behavioral are the result of some biochemical or Neuro-endocrine reactions
- As per music therapy- There are many music which affect our behaviour by making us Cool & Calm, Relax, Excited etc.
- If we feel relax or cool and clam-
- Scientific expansion-There is release of feel-good hormone (Endorphin) in brain which makes us cool and calm, relax.
- It mean music triggers the release of endorphin which make us relax.

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How music works-

Biochemical theory

- states that music is a sensory stimulus that is
- processed through the sense of hearing.
- Sound vibrations are chemically changed into nervous impulses that
- activate either the sympathetic or
- parasympathetic nervous system

Entrainment theory

- suggests that oscillations produced by music are
- received by the human energy field and
- various physiological systems entrain with or
- match the hertz (oscillation) of the music

Metaphysical theory suggests

- that music is divine in nature.

DCS theory of Neuroendocrine stimulation (Proposed by Dr. Dinesh C. Sharma) suggests

- Sound vibrations affect the physiology and biochemistry of humans by stimulating their neuro-endocrine system.

Effect of sound on biochemistry (Findings of my research work)-

Parameters	Rat(In lab)			Humans(Volunteers)		
	Sound "A"	Sound "B"	Sound "C"	Sound "A"	Sound "B"	Sound "C"
Adrenalin	↑ S	↓ S	↑ S	↑ NS	↓ NS	↑ NS
Cortisol	↓ S	↓ NS	↓ S	↓ S	↓ NS	↓ S
Endorphin	↑ HS	↓ NS	↑ NS	↑ NS	↓ S	↑ NS
Testosterone	↑ Male S ↓ Female	↑ Male NS ↓ Female	↑ Male S ↓ Female	↑ Male NS ↓ Female	↑ Male NS ↓ Female	↑ Male S ↓ Female
Progesterone	↓ S	↓ NS	↓ S	↓ NS	↓ NS	↓ NS
TG	↓ NS	↓ NS	↓ S	↓ NS	↓ NS	↓ NS
CHO	↓ S	↓ S	↓ S	↓ S	↓ NS	↓ S
LDL	↓ NS	↓ NS	↓ S	↓ S	↓ NS	↓ S
HDL	↑ S	↑ S	↑ NS	↑ HS	↑ S	↑ NS
Delivery time	↓ S	↓ S	↓ S	X	X	X
Group activity	↑ S	↑ NS	↑ S	X	X	X
NS = non significant HS = Highly significant ↓ = Decrease S = significant ↑ = Increase						

Discussion-

Now it's clear from the findings of music therapy research going around the world that music has the power to affect the physiology of living. Music therapy is very useful in the treatment of infant, old age and pregnant, when physicians are normally avoided to prescribe a drug except in case of emergency. It is also very useful to control anxiety and BP in Preoperative and postoperative conditions. The limitation of music therapy is that it can be used only to cure disorders not diseases and it cannot use in case of emergency. In my research I observed the Significant ($P < 0.001$ to $P < 0.05$) decrease in serum total cholesterol level in both human. In most cases Non Significant decrease in triglycerides has been observed except in sound "C" where significant decrease observed. Lipid bound proteins are called lipoproteins. Lipoproteins are found in plasma and their function is to transport lipids. Lipoprotein includes VLDL, LDL and HDL. In the present study VLDL and LDL are decrease Non-significantly except in case of sound "C". The HDL significantly increased in most cases. The decrease of serum triglycerides, cholesterol are directly correlated with decrease of LDL and VLDL. The decreases of various lipids are indicative of good health and support the view that sound can be used as a drug to control various lipid parameters. I also observed the increase the adrenalin level in both rat and human, whereas cortisol level found to be decreased.

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